

Who Needs Big Data? Small-Data Flux Reconstruction via Green's Functions and Ex-Core Detectors

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ABSTRACT

Accurate reconstruction of core power distributions is essential for the safe and autonomous operation of advanced and microreactor systems. Yet the limited survivability of in-core sensors under high-temperature, corrosive, and radiation-intense environments restricts direct measurements. This work presents a physics-directed, small-data framework that reconstructs three-dimensional neutron flux fields from ex-core measurements by coupling the Green's-function formulation of neutron diffusion with a neural-network representation. Instead of learning reactor behavior from extensive synthetic datasets, the proposed method learns the reactor's intrinsic transfer kernel—its Green's function; once retrieved, it serves as a universal physical descriptor linking boundary flux and gradient data to interior flux distributions. A neural network with layers enforcing physical constraints is trained to approximate this kernel, enabling real-time flux reconstruction during power operation using only ex-core signals. High-fidelity OpenMC simulations on a test case derived from PUR-1 reactor at Purdue University demonstrate average fractional flux errors below 5% using compact datasets and minimal sensor requirements. By embedding reactor physics directly into the learning process, the framework removes the dependence on massive datasets, minimizes instrumentation intrusiveness, and enables scalable, data-efficient diagnostics for next-generation nuclear systems.

Keywords: Physics-directed machine learning, Ex-core detectors, Green's function, Advanced reactors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Real-time reconstruction of core power distributions is fundamental to ensuring safety, performance optimization, and autonomous control. Conventional monitoring strategies in Light-Water Reactors rely on extensive in-core detector networks that provide direct measurements of local power and reactivity [1]. However, the harsh environments of advanced and microreactor systems—characterized by high temperatures, corrosive coolants, and intense radiation fields—severely limit the useful life of such instrumentation. The resulting scarcity of in-core data presents a major obstacle to real-time core diagnostics and feedback control in next-generation reactors [2]. The traditional approach of simulating a wide range of operating scenarios with high-fidelity neutronic models and then deriving surrogate models for use during operation is inherently limited. It demands massive training datasets, offers little adaptability to unmodeled conditions, and cannot readily capture configuration-specific deviations such as control rod maneuvers or localized material changes. During operation, real-time sensor data must be continuously assimilated into the model, allowing it to refine its predictions as the system evolves rather than depending solely on offline calculations performed under design-basis conditions.

To address these limitations, this work proposes a physics-directed, small-data framework for reconstructing three-dimensional neutron-flux fields from ex-core measurements by embedding a Green's-function formulation into the learning process. For this proof-of-concept, we adopt a one-group diffusion description, since ex-core signals are energy integrated and do not provide spectral resolution. The Green's kernel acts as a universal propagator that can be used to map boundary information (scalar

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flux and outward current) to interior flux distributions, enabling reuse across operating conditions once a reference kernel is identified. To implement this idea efficiently, we parameterize the Green's kernel with an artificial neural network (ANN). Because inference requires evaluating the kernel over many point pairs (\vec{r}, \vec{r}') , a compact and differentiable representation is essential. Neural networks scale to large collocation sets and allow physics-motivated properties to be enforced through the architecture and loss. Alternatives such as Gaussian processes or kernel methods can be prohibitively expensive at scale, and tree-based models do not readily accommodate differentiable, physics-based regularization. Simulations on a simplified Purdue University Reactor One (PUR-1) geometry show accurate reconstruction of core power distributions using compact training datasets and limited sensor coverage, and complementary experimental efforts indicate the feasibility of acquiring the boundary quantities required by the algorithm. Overall, the proposed approach lays the groundwork for a data-efficient diagnostic technique to support real-time monitoring, control, and fault detection in advanced and microreactor systems.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: GREEN'S FUNCTION BASIS FOR FLUX RECONSTRUCTION

2.1. Role of the Green's Function in Flux Reconstruction

This section summarizes the forward model and the Green's-function relations that link boundary measurements to the interior neutron-flux field, providing the foundation for the proposed reconstruction method. For clarity, we present the derivation for a simplified, steady-state, zero-power configuration and neglect thermal feedback and isotopic depletion. Consistent with the rationale given in the Introduction, we adopt a one-group diffusion equation, which captures the energy-integrated behavior accessible to ex-core instrumentation (Eq. 1).

$$\nabla \cdot [D(\vec{r})\nabla\phi(\vec{r})] - \Sigma_a(\vec{r})\phi(\vec{r}) + \nu\Sigma_f(\vec{r})\phi(\vec{r}) = 0, \quad \vec{r} \in V \quad (1)$$

This approximation is physically meaningful yet computationally tractable for interpreting boundary-driven monitoring data. Importantly, Eq. (1) defines a linear diffusion operator, so the principle of superposition applies, and a corresponding Green's function exists for the chosen domain and boundary conditions. Although computing the Green's function explicitly is generally impractical for realistic heterogeneous geometries [3], its existence enables an integral representation that expresses the interior flux in terms of boundary quantities and volumetric sources, which we exploit in the reconstruction framework.

When a control rod is inserted, a scattering-dominated region is replaced by a strongly absorbing material, altering both the diffusion coefficient D and the absorption cross section Σ_a (Eq. 2). These spatial perturbations are captured by recasting them as a domain-wide effective source term $Q(\vec{r})$, as defined in Eq. 3.

$$\Sigma_a \rightarrow \Sigma_a + \delta\Sigma_a, D \rightarrow D + \delta D \quad (2)$$

$$Q(\vec{r}) = [\nu\Sigma_f(\vec{r}) - \delta\Sigma_a(\vec{r})]\phi(\vec{r}) + \nabla \cdot [\delta D(\vec{r})\nabla\phi(\vec{r})] \quad (3)$$

In Eq. 4, non-homogeneous neutron diffusion equation is reported, and the corresponding diffusion operator (\mathcal{L}) is defined. For simplicity, the spatial dependence of the variables is omitted.

$$\mathcal{L}\phi = -\nabla \cdot (D\nabla\phi) + \Sigma_a\phi = Q \quad (4)$$

Because \mathcal{L} is a linear and elliptic operator, the Green's function $G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}')$ may be defined as the system's response to a unit point source at \vec{r}' (Eq. 5).

$$\mathcal{L}G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') = -\delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}') \text{ in } V \quad (5)$$

The Green's function is defined over a pair of spatial coordinates representing two distinct physical roles: the field point \vec{r} , where the neutron flux is measured, and the source point \vec{r}' , which denotes the location of the perturbation or boundary excitation. Within the context of the present reconstruction

framework, the source points correspond to the ex-core detector locations that provide measurable flux, whereas the field points represent the in-core positions where the neutron flux must be inferred.

2.2. Kirchhoff Helmholtz Equation and Green's Function Derivation

Eq. 6 defines the Kirchhoff-Helmholtz (K-H) equation for the one-speed neutron diffusion model.

$$\phi(\vec{r}) = \int_S [G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') D(\vec{r}') \nabla_n \phi(\vec{r}') - \phi(\vec{r}') D(\vec{r}') \nabla_n G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}')] dS_{\vec{r}'} + \int_V G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') Q(\vec{r}') dV_{\vec{r}'}, \quad \vec{r} \in V \quad (6)$$

where S is the domain boundary and ∇_n indicates differentiation along the boundary normal. This formulation recasts in-core neutron-flux estimation as an inverse boundary-value problem: the flux is uniquely determined by boundary data and the Green's kernel, which embeds the transport physics and geometric effects. In ex-core monitoring, the boundary data correspond to measurable peripheral signals: the scalar flux and the outward neutron current. We therefore treat reconstruction of the Green's function as a learning task, training a neural network to approximate G so that Eq. 6 is satisfied across the training set. The goal is to identify a mapping between any two points $\vec{r}, \vec{r}' \in V$ yielding the Green's function $\hat{G}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}')$, which relates accessible data at the boundary S to the internal neutron field (Eq. 7). Further details on the formulation and well-posedness are provided in [4].

$$(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') \xrightarrow{\text{mapping}} \hat{G}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') \quad (7)$$

2.3. Fundamental Properties of the Green's Kernel

The usefulness of the Green's kernel in neutron-flux reconstruction arises from the mathematical properties that reflect the physics of neutron diffusion. In a bounded domain with appropriate BCs, the Green's function associated with the one-group diffusion operator satisfies the properties listed below.

- **Self-Adjointness and Reciprocity**

When parameters D , Σ_a and $\nu\Sigma_f$ are real and positive, \mathcal{L} is a self-adjoint operator under the standard $L^2(V)$ inner product $\langle f, g \rangle = \int_V f g dV$ for functions satisfying the imposed BCs (Eq. 8), implying reciprocity of the Green's kernel (Eq. 9). This relation implies that the response at \vec{r} due to a source at \vec{r}' is identical to the response at \vec{r}' when the source is placed at \vec{r} —a fundamental feature of diffusive transport.

$$\langle u, \mathcal{L}v \rangle = \langle \mathcal{L}u, v \rangle \quad (\text{same BCs}) \quad (8)$$

$$G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') = G(\vec{r}', \vec{r}) \quad (9)$$

- **Positivity**

For diffusion operators with positive coefficients, the maximum principle guarantees that $G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') \geq 0$ throughout V . Physically, this means that a positive neutron source cannot induce negative flux anywhere in the domain; every contribution adds constructively to the total field. This property is essential when the Green's function is used as a kernel in machine-learning reconstruction, as it ensures monotonicity.

- **Real-valuedness**

Because all coefficients of \mathcal{L} are real, its eigenvalues and eigenfunctions form a real spectrum. The Green's function, being the kernel of a self-adjoint operator, is therefore purely real. This guarantees that the learned neural representation remains in the physical space of measurable quantities and avoids unphysical complex-valued artifacts.

- **Universality**

Once the operator \mathcal{L} , the domain geometry and the BCs are specified, the Green's function is uniquely determined and does not depend on the particular source term. Accordingly, the network is not learning a mere statistical correlation, but a *physics-grounded transfer kernel* that maps

boundary flux and gradient measurements to the interior neutron-flux field. This capability underpins the *small-data paradigm*: once trained on a compact, representative dataset, the learned kernel can be reused to reconstruct flux for arbitrary control-rod configurations using only boundary inputs.

2.4. Effective Source and Boundary Condition Treatment

BCs play a decisive role in defining the Green's function, as they determine both the mathematical uniqueness of the solution and the physical coupling between ex-core measurements and the in-core neutron flux. During reactor operation, both the boundary quantities and the operator coefficients (i.e., D , Σ_a and $\nu\Sigma_f$) vary with control-rod insertion and thermo-hydraulic conditions. Because the Green's kernel inherently depends on the BCs, each operational state would, in principle, require a distinct kernel. To maintain a single, reusable Green's function, the boundary-value problems corresponding to different reactor states must be reformulated to share the same operator and BCs, differing only in the source term.

- **Effective Source term:**

As discussed in Section 2, the variations introduced by control-rod movement or localized material changes are captured through an effective source term (Eq. 3). Operational variations are expressed as inhomogeneous forcings of an otherwise identical \mathcal{L} operator, allowing a single Green's kernel to serve all scenarios.

- **Consistency of Boundary Conditions:**

BCs must be regularized to a common reference form. For simplicity and mathematical convenience, homogeneous Dirichlet conditions are adopted. This is accomplished through the *lifting method*, in which an auxiliary function $\psi(\vec{r})$ —typically a smooth polynomial or harmonic interpolation—is introduced to reproduce the boundary values (Eq. 10). The total flux field is expressed in Eq. 11.

$$\psi(\vec{r})|_S = \phi(\vec{r})|_S \quad (10)$$

$$\phi(\vec{r}) = u(\vec{r}) + \psi(\vec{r}) \quad (11)$$

with $u|_S = 0$. Substituting this decomposition into the diffusion equation transfers all boundary effects into a modified source term $\tilde{Q} = Q - \mathcal{L}\psi$, thereby preserving the operator form while maintaining consistent boundary treatment across all operating states.

3. PHYSICS-DIRECTED NEURAL-NETWORK FORMULATION

3.1. Implementation and Workflow

The theoretical formulation introduced in Section 2 is embedded through a neural-network model that numerically approximates the Green's kernel. By embedding the K–H relation, the network is driven not only to match reference data but also to satisfy the governing neutron-diffusion physics, resulting in an interpretable and reusable propagator. The workflow is displayed in Figure 1. Inputs include the control-rod configuration—which determines the effective source term—together with the domain geometry and the imposed BCs. Target values are provided by a compact set of reference flux fields generated in high-fidelity simulations. From these, the network learns a Green's-function response that maps boundary information to the unmeasured interior flux distribution over the monitored domain. Architecture and training specifics are not detailed here, as the focus of this work is on demonstrating the physics-directed learning concept rather than a particular implementation. Two main components define the loss function to be minimized during training:

- **Flux-reconstruction Accuracy**

The first term is the mean squared error (MSE) between the reconstructed flux (\hat{u}) and the measured flux (u) evaluated at both boundary collocation points and interior locations. This component penalizes discrepancies in predicted flux values, ensuring accuracy throughout the domain.

- **Regularization of the Green's Function**

The second term penalizes the magnitude and spatial gradients of the learned Green's kernel, discouraging excessively large responses and sharp variations. Importantly, the regularization acts on the kernel of the selected reference diffusion operator, which is expected to be spatially smooth, while rod-driven localized features are captured primarily through the effective source term and boundary inputs rather than through non-smooth structure in the kernel itself.

The loss function for the training set is defined in Eq. 12.

$$\text{Loss} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [\hat{u}(\vec{r}_i) - u(\vec{r}_i)]^2 + \frac{\alpha}{N^2} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{P}} (|\hat{G}(\vec{r}_i, \vec{r}_j')|^2 + \|\nabla_{\vec{r}_i} \hat{G}(\vec{r}_i, \vec{r}_j')\|^2) \quad (12)$$

where $N = N_C + N_P$ is the total number of boundary collocation (N_C) and interior anchoring (N_P) points, and $\mathcal{P} = \{(i, j): 1 \leq i, j \leq N, i \neq j\}$ denotes the set of point pairs used to evaluate the kernel regularization term. The diagonal pairs are excluded because the Green's function exhibits a singular behavior as $\vec{r}_i \rightarrow \vec{r}_j'$; penalizing the resulting large magnitude or steep gradients would therefore suppress an expected feature of the kernel and bias training. The weight α controls the influence of the regularization term and was set to $1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in this study. In practice, α is chosen by validation on held-out configurations to avoid oversmoothing and can be reduced or made spatially adaptive if reconstruction near strong absorbers is underpredicted. For the test set, we report only the flux-reconstruction accuracy term as the evaluation metric.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the physics-directed neural-network workflow.

3.2. Experimental Measurement of Boundary Flux Gradient

The experimental measurement of the boundary conditions represents one of the primary challenges to the practical deployment of the proposed method. To date, a detector that directly resolves flux gradients under reactor operating conditions has not been widely demonstrated. In the late 1990s, Pázsit showed that gradient information could significantly enhance core-monitoring performance and introduced an early detector concept [5]. Later studies explored the use of detector arrays to infer flux gradients, notably in safeguards applications [6]. Building on these earlier efforts, Argonne National Laboratory (ANL) and Purdue University developed a compact *quadrupole* detector designed to resolve directional components of the neutron-flux gradient near the core boundary. The instrument comprises four identical sensing elements arranged symmetrically about a central axis; differential signals from opposing elements provide a direct estimate of the local flux-gradient vector. A prototype was designed

and fabricated in July–August 2025 and installed at PUR-1 (Figure 2). An experimental campaign to collect boundary flux-gradient data and incorporate measured signals into training and validation is in progress and will be reported in future work. Additional details are provided in [7].

Figure 2. Design and fabrication of the 3D-printed positioning and stabilization system used for mounting the irradiation wires in the quadrupole detector.

4. VALIDATION AND PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

The performance of the proposed small-data framework was evaluated using a simplified geometry derived from PUR-1 as a test-case. The goal was to demonstrate that a Green’s kernel learned from a compact dataset can accurately reconstruct three-dimensional flux distributions under different operating conditions using only boundary information. A high-fidelity OpenMC model was developed to generate training and test datasets [8]. The geometry consisted of a 30.48x30.48x68.58 cm fuel region surrounded by a 7.62-cm. graphite reflector. Two control-rod configurations were analyzed:

- **Scenario #1 (training):** all rods fully inserted ($z_1 = z_2 = z_3 = 68.58$ cm);
- **Scenario #2 (test):** partial withdrawal of the three rods at different depths ($z_1 = 53.34$ cm, $z_2 = 60.96$ cm, $z_3 = 60.96$ cm).

Boundary flux and gradient data from Scenario #1 were used as network inputs, and interior fluxes served as targets. The boundary conditions were characterized at 288 locations for both training and testing. After training, the same kernel was used to reconstruct the flux field for Scenario #2 without retraining. Two cases were analyzed to assess the sensitivity of the reconstruction to in-core data availability during training:

- **Test #1:** 128 interior points;
- **Test #2:** 45 interior points.

Across the 144 voxels within the active core region (4x4x9 grid), the network achieved mean fractional errors of 4.0% in *Test #1* and 3.06% in *Test #2*, with no observable systematic bias (Figure 3). These results demonstrate that satisfactory reconstruction accuracy can be maintained even when the number of interior sensors is reduced by two-thirds—a key requirement for advanced reactors with limited instrumentation access.

Figure 4 shows the estimated Green’s function, evaluated over all coordinate pairs formed from 288 boundary collocation points and 45 interior anchoring points (*Test #2*). Finite spikes appear along the diagonal $\vec{r}' = \vec{r}$, reflecting the Green’s function singularity at coincident coordinates. In the analytical limit, the Green’s function diverges as $\vec{r}' \rightarrow \vec{r}$. By contrast, the discretized formulation assigns each coordinate to a voxel of finite volume, regularizing this behavior; the singularity is numerically smoothed, resulting in finite yet sharply peaked values. The learned kernel exhibits the expected physical properties—reciprocity, positivity, and real-valuedness—evident from its symmetric distribution about the diagonal and its strictly positive magnitude.

Figure 3. Test #2 results: predicted neutron-flux distribution in the core active region (left) and corresponding fractional deviations from reference values (right).

Figure 4. Learned Green's function for Test #2, evaluated over 288 collocation points and 45 interior points.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces a physics-directed, small-data framework for reconstructing three-dimensional neutron-flux fields in reactor cores using ex-core measurements. By embedding the Green's-function formulation of neutron diffusion within a neural-network representation, the approach replaces the reliance on large synthetic datasets with a compact, physics-constrained learning problem. Once trained, the resulting kernel acts as a universal propagator, mapping boundary flux and gradient data to interior power distributions under arbitrary control-rod configurations.

Numerical validation using high-fidelity simulations of a simplified geometry demonstrated reconstruction errors below 5%, even when the number of interior training points was reduced by two-thirds. These results confirm the robustness and data efficiency of the proposed formulation and its direct relevance to advanced and microreactor systems, where in-core instrumentation is limited or short-lived. Beyond reconstructing static flux maps, the method opens a pathway toward real-time reactor diagnostics. The proposed small-data paradigm provides a scalable and interpretable foundation for resilient monitoring of next-generation nuclear reactors. It shifts the focus of reactor

diagnostics from collecting more data to collecting the right data, i.e., those that best inform the physics already encoded in the system.

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